

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review On Face Scrub

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 21 May 2024

Published: 29 May 2024

Keywords:

Herbal scrub, exfoliants,
phyto ingredients,
antioxidant, acne, skin.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.11388792

ABSTRACT

Many of the marketed products, when applied topically, result in skin dryness after prolonged usage, which shortens the duration of acne and redness. Using a scrub made entirely of herbal substances will solve this issue and improve the skin's washing, softening, moisturizing, and fairness. Natural or herbal cosmetics are made using natural substances to treat wrinkles, acne, and oil secretion management. Antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-aging plant parts are typically found in herbal cosmeceuticals. Cosmetics are products that affect the biological function of the skin, and herbal cosmetics are the safest to use regularly with no known negative effects.

INTRODUCTION

Items referred to as "Herbal Cosmetics" are prepared with various cosmetic substances that are allowed, serving as a foundation for the use of one or more herbal ingredients to provide "characteristic corrective preferences." Cosmetic manufacturers began updating the word "cosmeceuticals" in the 1990s to refer to over-the-counter skin care products that added active ingredients derived from plants, such as coenzyme, retinoic acid, alpha-hydroxy acid, and ascorbic acid, to claim therapeutic benefits. These active compounds provide several benefits, including improved skin suppleness, prevention of UV ray damage through antioxidant properties, reduction of wrinkles, and inhibition of collagen

deterioration. The Greek term "kosmetikos," which means to have authority, order, or decorating skill, is where the word "cosmetic" originated. The development of beauty care products is a story that has been told continuously throughout human history. In ancient times, around 3000 BC, man utilized colors to entice the creatures he wanted to pursue. He also used colors to protect himself from attacks by decorating his body and skin to frighten opponents, both human and animal. The health, routines, employment schedules, weather, and maintenance were factors that affected people's skin and hair beauty. Summertime dehydration from prolonged heat contact to the skin results in wrinkles, blotches, blemishes, pigmentation, and sunburns. Extreme cold can damage skin and

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

hairs, resulting in cracks, wounds, maceration, contamination, and hair loss. All age groups have skin disorders, which can be brought on by exposure to chemicals, biological toxins found in the environment, or organisms. In addition, some skin diseases might worsen as a result of malnutrition. The information and data of nature compiled in the ayurveda was the only thing they could rely on. Numerous plants and herbs were used by the science of ayurveda to create beauty care products that protect against external influences and enhance appearance. The Drug and Cosmetics Act defines beauty care products as items that are meant to be poured, rubbed, powdered, sprayed, incorporated into, or otherwise varied goods.

DEFINITION OF COSMETICS :-

The Drugs and Cosmetics Act defines cosmetics as articles meant to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, sprayed, introduced into, or applied in any other way to the human body or any part of it for the purposes of cleaning, beautifying, enhancing attractiveness, or altering appearance. The cosmetic is not covered by the drug license preview.

DEFINITION OF HERBAL COSMETICS :-

These are cosmetics made using plant-based ingredients that have a cosmetic effect. The moderate action and non-toxic nature of botanicals have led to an expansion in their use in beauty care products in recent times. Both natural and phyto-ingredients are used in cosmetics. Products classified as natural include oils, extracts, secretions, etc. Pure substances derived from various processes are referred to as phyto-ingredients.

Herbal Cosmetics for Various Types of Skin

1.For Dry Skin

Example of Herbs

- Rubia Cardifolia (Manjista),

- Triphala,
- Tulsi,
- Glycerihza glabra in sesame oil.
- Banana or avocado pulp.

Fruit face mask

2. For Sensitive Skin

Example of Herbs

- Usheero,
- Curcuma longa,
- Triphala,
- Azadirecta indica mustaka,
- Nimba in coconut oil.
- Fruit face mask
- Banana or pineapple pulp.

3. For Oily Skin

Example of Herbs

- Tulsi,
- Idhora,
- Nimba,
- Curcuma longa.
- Fruit face mask
- Strawberry or papaya pulp.

Ideal Properties of Scrub :-

An ideal scrub is accepted to possess the following properties [8] It should be Non toxic Possess small gritty particles Mild abrasive Non irritating Non sticky Able to remove dead skin cell Healthy, glowing skin, minimise spore, reduces breakout and acne, Hides wrinkles Allows absorption of the products, improve your tan, Maintain body pH. Scrubbing is the removal of dry/ dead skin cells on the surface of the skin and is one of the most important of skincare routine for face. Scrubbing not only helps many skin problems, it also increases blood circulation, which in turn helps you to achieve healthy and glowing skin. Abrasive scrub cleansers are used for mechanical exfoliation.

The Disadvantages of Scrub :-

Both vigorous scrubbing movements and chemicals have the potential to irritate skin,

resulting in redness and inflammation. The chemicals in the synthetic scrubs might potentially cause allergic responses in people with sensitive skin. Excessive washing may lead to open pores

that are simultaneously exposed to UV radiation and pollutants. Additionally, it makes your skin more vulnerable to sunburn and infections.

Herbal Scrub	Synthetic scrub
Herbal products are completely free from all the harmful chemicals as they are naturally derived.	Synthetic product are maybe slightly harmful chemicals as they are Synthetically derived.
Herbal refer to products that are prepared from plants for their medicinal value	Synthetic refer to product that are prepared from chemicals
safe to use as compared to chemical-based cosmetics.	They may be harmful for sensitive skin
Synthetic refer to product that are prepared from chemicals	More side effect than herbal product
E.g. Plum Green Tea gentle revival face scrub	E.g. Cetaphil Extra gentle daily scrub

1. Neem leaves powder :

Synonym –

Neem

Biological source :

It consists of dried leaves of *Azadirctia indica* belonging to family Meliaceae.

Description Colour –

Green Odour - Pungent Taste – Bitter

Chief chemical constituents

Nimbinin, Nimbidin, Quercetin

Uses

Skin toner, lightens skin blemishes, Remove blackheads

2. Tulsi leaves powder :-

Synonym-

Tulsi

Biological source –

It consists of dried leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* L belonging to family Lamiaceae.

Description Colour –

Green Odour - Aromatic Taste – Pungent

Chief Chemical constituents –

oleanolic acid, ursolic acid, rosmarinic acid

Uses

Prevents acne and pimples, Improve skin texture, Cleanser.

3. Turmeric powder :-

Synonym-

Curcuma longa

Biological source –

It consists of dried rhizomes of Curcuma longa belonging to family Zingiberaceae.

Description –

Colour - Yellow Odour - Aromatic Taste – Bitter

Chief chemical constituents –

Curcumin, Curcuminoids

Uses –

Reduce acne, Glowing skin, Lightens skin.

4. Orange peel powder:-

Synonym –

Orange zest

Biological source –

It consists of dried fruits of Citrus sinensis belonging to family Rutaceae.

Description Colour-

Dark orange red Odour - Aromatic Taste – Bitter

Chief chemical constituents

Terpenes, Carotenoids, Flavonoids

Uses

Reduce skin marks, skin spots, help to skin whitening, Treat pimples, acne

5. Sandalwood powder :-

Synonym-

Sandalwood tree

Biological source –

It consists of dried bark of Santalum album belonging to family Santalaceae.

Description Colour-

Brown Odour - Aromatic Taste – Unpleasant

Chief chemical constituents

Santalol, Cedrol, Esters

Uses –

Soothe sunburn, remove suntan, Reduce signs of aging skin.

6. Multani mitti :-

Synonym-

Multan clay

Biological source

It consists of hydrous aluminum silicates (clay minerals) .

Description Colour-

White Odour - Pleasant Taste – Pleasant

Chief chemical constituents

Montmorillonite, Kaolinite, Attapulgit

Uses-

Nourishes skin, reduce oiliness, Remove blackheads.

WHAT IS EXFOLIANT ?

Exfoliation is the process by which a facial scrub removes dead skin cells from the skin by using tiny particles, beads, or chemicals. Exfoliants are the agents that are employed in exfoliation. Exfoliating compounds are used to get rid of dead skin cells and increase blood flow to the skin, leaving it looking refreshed and radiant. It helps to maintain a skin pore clean by keeping the face free of dust, debris, and oils. The skin can be exfoliated in two different methods. During exfoliation, the oldest dead skin cells are removed from the skin's surface. The word exfoliate, which means "to strip off leaves," is derived from Latin. Every facial includes exfoliation, which can be done chemically or mechanically with procedures like chemical peels or microdermabrasion. Exfoliants are frequently promoted as remedies that enhance health, beauty, or a young appearance.

METHODS :-

Collection and extraction of herbal extract

Phytochemical analysis

Quantitative estimations

Preparation of nanoparticles

Evaluation of nanoparticles

Evaluation of nanoparticles :-

- UV Visible spectroscopy
- Antioxidant studies
- Anti-microbial activity

Evaluation Parameters [14-15]:-

Colour:

The colour of the face scrub can be checked visually

Odour:

The odour of the scrub is checked by smelling it.

pH:

The pH of the product can be checked by applying it on ph paper.

Consistency:

Consistency can be determined manually.

Spreadability: $S = m \times l / t$

S = Spreadability m = Weight placed on slide

l = Length of the glass slide

t = Time taken in seconds

EXTRUDABILITY :-

A tiny quantity of scrub can be placed within a foldable ointment tube. One end remained open while the other was closed. On the closed side, a small amount of pressure can be used. It is possible to note the amount of scrub extruded and the extrusion time.

VISCOSITY :-

Brookfield viscometer is used to measure the viscosity of scrub.

IRRITABILITY :-

It has been discovered that a small amount of the scrub is non-irritating when applied to the skin and left on for a few minutes.

WASHABILITY :-

Applying formulations to the skin is simple, and they can be removed simply by washing with water. Gritfulness By putting the product on the skin, one may determine whether it contains any grit.

STABILITY STUDIES :-

Filling plastic containers with the scrub and setting them in a humidity room at 45°C and 75% relative humidity will test the formulation's stability. For three months, the formulation's stability can be examined one month at a time.

WHY THE HEBAL SCRUB :-

Herbal medication has a longer history of use and is more well-tolerated and accepted by patients. The only reliable source of pricey medications for the world's expanding population is medicinal plants, as they have a renewable supply. In addition to being safe to use, a herbal face scrub will exfoliate your skin, giving it a more radiant, healthy-looking appearance. Because face scrubs made of natural ingredients are completely safe to use and have no negative effects, you can purchase them in place of chemical ones. But you have to refrain from using a face scrub every day to exfoliate your skin. This is due to the possibility of cell damage that occurs from everyday exfoliation of the skin with scrubs, which can lead to rough skin. Thus, you ought to be aware of how to apply it and what to avoid. You may encourage the formation of collagen on your skin by exfoliating it with a herbal face scrub, which will make your skin appear smoother and more luminous. By using a herbal face scrub, you can prevent breakouts on your skin as well. Make sure that your skin is not peeling off

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HOW TO CITE: Manish Bhosale, Snehal Kothavale, Kishor Otari, A Review On Face Scrub, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 5, 1746-1752. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11388792>